

Perception of developers and users on the use of journey map in software requirements elicitation

Context: Requirements elicitation is a fundamental step in a software development process since it is at this stage that the software begins to be designed. In some situations, the problems related to the failure of the software development project are due to an incomplete requirements elicitation or failure, resulting in solutions that do not understand all the necessary functionalities or do not incorporate innovation. Despite the various techniques offered by Requirements Engineering, situations such as the growing market for applications and the need for innovation further increase the importance of understanding the user's different needs. Objective: In this paper, we investigated how the personas and journey map techniques are being used in requirements elicitation in both the literature and the industry, along with the positive and negative points of using these techniques. Method: We conducted systematic literature reviews to identify the personas and journey map techniques used in requirements elicitation in the literature and industry. In addition, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 27 software developers to investigate their perception of the use of journeys map and personas techniques in the requirements elicitation phase. Results: Twenty-three primary studies were identified that address journey map and personas techniques in software requirements elicitation. In addition, most respondents stated that using these techniques facilitates understanding the requirements, providing better integration, collaboration, and leveling of knowledge among the members of the software development teams. Conclusions: Our findings allow us to conclude that most software developers, users, and managers, consider that the journey map and personas techniques are effective in understanding the software requirements to be developed by the development teams.

1 RESULTS

We consolidated the main advantages and challenges related to journey map and personas mentioned by the primary study authors, as presented in Table 1.

Table 2 presents the list of topics used to guide interviews with software developers and users/managers.

The questions we asked the participants during the semi-structured interviews are presented in Table 3.

Table 1. Selected primary studies at SLR

ID	Ref	Advantages and Challenges
E1	[7]	It allows efficient information gathering, better process definition, identification of new touchpoints (journey map).
E2	[6]	Visualization of a complex process; identify the process flow through a joint effort between stakeholders and developers; identify and analyze individual process activities in more detail; involve all stakeholders. Challenges: the moderator must have some experience in moderating processes; for each user process in the project scope, a separate journey map must be created.
E3	[23]	Improves customer interaction, allowing you to identify each point of contact between the customer and the organization. Challenges: The journey map assumes that all customers in an organization experience the same organizational touchpoints and that everyone is equally important. There is no consolidation of the journey map.
E4	[12]	Journeys maps allow you to get users' points of view and gain insights into their experiences.
E5	[19]	They design an ideal experience that meets the main stakeholders' expectations, improve communication, and make it possible to identify opportunities and risks through personas and journey map.
E6	[18]	Journey map can be an effective method of enhancing user experience.
E7	[3]	Provide a common language for multidisciplinary teams. A challenge was stimulating introverted people's participation once they tend not to share ideas and be overshadowed by extroverted people's personalities (in journey maps and personas).
E8	[10]	Personas provide a human face to bring the team closer to potential end-users and help the development team understand the characteristics of a user group.
E9	[9]	Enable efficient design decisions to be made without generalization, and to communicate the users' knowledge. Challenges: Personas can't always help design the solution to the users' real needs.
E10	[2]	Personas can contain helpful information and can increase collaboration and knowledge exchange between development and client teams. The technique can improve the final result of the applications developed.
E11	[14]	The personas allowed to create and adapt different routes for a specific profile, identifying the users' difficulty levels, accessibility level, security level, and places. Through personas, it was possible to define the functional requirements.
E12	[8]	They help the team understand the characteristics of a group of users and propose solutions related to users' primary needs. Challenges: Persona descriptions often contain many details related to personal characteristics and little information relevant to the software to be developed. This can limit the use and acceptance of the personas technique.
E13	[1]	Personas can help communicate between project members, promoting greater consensus and empathy in interdisciplinary teams, helping and accelerating decision making.
E14	[15]	Through using the personas technique in the requirement analysis phase, the developers can better understand the user and improve the system usability.
E15	[4]	Persona creation methods enrich requirements engineering practices. Challenges: there is no single persona approach that is applicable in all contexts.
E16	[20]	Personas allow obtaining acceptance criteria to describe the scope of an agile requirement.
E17	[11]	Challenges: "It is necessary to achieve equilibrium between information about the persona's personal characteristics and the features that really help in the application design."
E18	[13]	"The benefit of employing the Personas technique is to place the user at the center of the development process, which keeps the teams informed about end-users' requirements".
E19	[22]	The authors did not mention the advantages and disadvantages of using the personas and journey map techniques.
E20	[21]	The biggest challenge is the different perceptions of users regarding the requirements.
E21	[17]	Benefits of personas include user immersion, communication about customers among decision-makers, and personas as mental models to keep customers in mind constantly. The main challenge is that the technique accuracy is difficult to validate. There is criticism toward personas under four primary constructs: credibility, consistency, completeness, usefulness, and willingness to use.
E22	[5]	The creation of personas and journey maps are helpful to synthesize the research findings or ideate. In addition, visual artifacts from Design Thinking activities such as personas or journey maps provide transparency and knowledge sharing.
E23	[16]	Challenges: the effect of bias on persona creation and when personas are applied in actual use cases, there has been a lack of perceived credibility.

Table 2. Topics discussed during the interviews

Demographic Information of Software Developers	
1.	Time of experience as a software developer
2.	Phase in which they work in software development (elicitation, analysis, design, etc.)
3.	Level of Knowledge in relation to Design Thinking
4.	Level of Knowledge in relation to the journey map and personas techniques
Demographic Information of Users/Software Managers	
1.	Amount of projects where journey map was applied
Perception of Software Developers	
1.	Average time spent in requirements elicitation using the journey map technique
2.	Journey map steps executed or customized
3.	Reason for non-compliance with the journey map stages
Perception of Software Users/Managers	
1.	Average time spent on the journey map
2.	Satisfaction with the time spent
3.	Knowledge of the business
4.	Knowledge of requirements
Positive Points, Challenges and Suggestions from Software Developers, Users/Managers	
1.	Business knowledge and learning
2.	Process, steps and failures
3.	Challenges and suggestions

Table 3. Questions asked during the semi-structured interviews

ID	Question
Q1	The use of persona and journey map facilitates the identification of the steps of the users process and their experiences or pains.
Q2	The use of persona and journey map facilitates the learning of user processes within the project.
Q3	All processes, needs and perceptions are better understood at the journey map.
Q4	Business Knowledge and requirements has been improved with the journey map technique.
Q5	The use of persona and journey map makes it easy to identify any flaw in the process, or even the lack of it.
Q6	It was possible to identify knowledge gaps that need to be addressed.
Q7	The use of journey map and persona enabled greater knowledge management between users and the software development team.
Q8	Tacit knowledge has been transformed in explicit for all participants in the persona and journey map techniques.

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